

COMPARATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL POTENTIALS OF ETHANOL EXTRACTS OF *Moringa oleifera* SEEDS AND *Azadirachta indica* LEAVES AGAINST FOUR BACTERIAL PATHOGENS

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Abstract

This study compared the phytochemical profile and antibacterial potentials of ethanolic extracts of *M. oleifera* seeds with *A. indica* leaves against four public health significant bacteria. The phytochemical screening was done using standard qualitative and quantitative tests. The antibacterial activity was evaluated against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella spp*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* via agar well and broth dilution method. Results showed that both plant extracts contained major phytochemicals: alkaloids, saponins, and flavonoids with *A. indica* extract having a significantly higher concentration for all (21.31 mg/g - 193.15 mg/g) than *M. oleifera* extract (4.76 mg/g – 37.45 mg/g) while tannins and phenols were absent in *M. oleifera* extract and glycosides in *A. indica*. Both extracts exhibited clear dose-dependent antimicrobial activity ($p < 0.01$). The ethanolic extract of *M. oleifera* had smaller zones of inhibition at higher concentrations (8 mm – 9 mm) compared to the zones of inhibition (10 mm – 15 mm) for *A. indica*. The MIC values for both extracts were similar for *E. coli* (25 mg/mL) while *A. indica* had a lower value for all others (25 mg/mL) except *S. aureus* (50 mg/mL). Both plant extracts function as reliable sources of antibacterial compounds in the formulation of new antimicrobial substances and therapeutic products. Beyond their therapeutic potential, these findings highlight the biotechnological relevance of the studied plants. Their antimicrobial properties may be exploited in the development of eco-friendly food preservatives, sustainable biopesticides, and water purification technologies.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica*, *Moringa oleifera*, antibacterial activity, phytochemicals, MIC, MBC, pathogens, bacteria.

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Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance is a global public health threat that was responsible for approximately 4.95 million deaths in 2019 with 1.95 million due to resistant bacteria alone. The highest burden, 27.3 deaths in every 100,000 persons was recorded in Western sub-Saharan Africa (Murray et al., 2022). The growing resistance to commonly used antibiotics has increased infections, leading to higher treatment costs, and increased mortality rates making it necessary to obtain alternative interventions (Allemailem, 2021).

Before synthetic antibiotics, plant-based remedies were used to manage most bacterial infections, and many commonly used drugs today have their origins in plant-derived compounds (Napagoda and Wijesundara, 2022). Consequently, medicinal plants continue to attract considerable scientific interest as potential sources of novel antimicrobial agents and other bioactive compounds. Medicinal plants such as *Moringa oleifera* and *Azadirachta indica* have been identified as rich sources of phytochemicals, including alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenols. These phytochemicals exhibit antimicrobial activity through various means, including cell membrane disruption, nucleic acid synthesis inhibition, and metabolic pathways interference (Khameneh et al., 2021).

Moringa oleifera is an indigenous plant of the Indian subcontinent. It is currently grown across several warm regions of the world and is used for its nutritional and healing abilities. Although various parts of the plant have been investigated for their biological activities (Bichi et al., 2012, Kheir et al., 2014, Osuala et al., 2024), the seeds were selected for this study because they contain high concentrations of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and antimicrobial peptides. In addition, *M. oleifera* seeds have demonstrated antimicrobial activity against a wide range of pathogenic microorganisms and possess coagulating properties that have attracted interest for water treatment applications (Kashyap et al., 2022). These characteristics make the seeds a promising candidate for the development of alternative antimicrobial agents.

Azadirachta indica (Neem) is a medicinal plant widely used in traditional healthcare systems. Among its various parts, the leaves were

selected because they are readily available, renewable, and rich in biologically active constituents such as flavonoids, phenolics, terpenoids, and limonoids. These compounds have been associated with antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antiparasitic activities (Mohanasundaram and Antoneyraj, 2025; Tufail et al., 2025). Furthermore, neem leaves have been extensively utilized in traditional medicine for the treatment of infectious diseases, making it a prime selection for evaluating antimicrobial efficacy against bacterial pathogens.

Although both *M. oleifera* and *A. indica* have been extensively studied individually (Kashyap et al., 2022; Mohanasundaram and Antoneyraj, 2025), differences in plant parts, extraction methods, and test organisms make direct comparisons between their antibacterial activities difficult. Therefore, comparative studies using standardized extraction and testing procedures are necessary to better evaluate their relative antimicrobial potential. Therefore, this study comparatively evaluated the bioactive phytochemical composition and antibacterial potential of *M. oleifera* seeds and *A. indica* leaves ethanolic extracts against Gram-negative (*Salmonella spp*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) and Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) bacterial pathogens.

Materials and Methods

Plant Material Preparation and Extraction

Fresh *M. oleifera* seeds and *A. indica* leaves were collected from Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria. They were washed to remove impurities, and the outer coats of the *Moringa* seeds were removed. Afterwards, both leaves and seeds were shade-dried, ground into powder, and stored until use.

The ethanolic extracts of both plant samples were prepared by macerating as described by Abubakar and Haque (2020). The prepared samples, 100 g each, were soaked in 500 mL of 70% ethanol in separate conical flasks and the mixture was shaken intermittently at 100 rpm. After 72 h, it was filtered and the filtrates concentrated on a water bath at 50 °C. The condensed extracts were stored until needed for further use.

Phytochemical Assessments of Plant Extracts

Tests were conducted to identify active phytochemicals; tannins, alkaloids, phenols, flavonoids, saponins, glycosides, and terpenoids in the extracts. Quantitative estimations were performed for alkaloids, total flavonoid and phenolic contents, saponins, and tannins. All procedures used for both qualitative and quantitative tests followed standard methods as described by Adekanmi et al. (2020) and were carried out in triplicates.

Detection of Flavonoids (Ammonia Test)

Approximately 0.50 g of extract was treated with 10 mL of ethyl acetate and gently heated in a waterbath for about 3 min. The mixture filtered, and the filtrate (4 mL) was combined with diluted ammonia solution (1 mL). A yellow colour development was considered evidence of flavonoids.

Detection of Saponins (Frothing and Emulsion Test)

One gram (1 g) of extract was mixed with distilled water (10 mL). After the mixture was filtered, five milliliters of the filtrate (5 mL) was diluted further and shaken well to observe the formation of persistent froth. Addition of olive oil followed by the development of a stable emulsion supported the presence of saponins.

Terpenoids (Salkowski) Test

Approximately 0.50 mL of the extract was mixed with chloroform in a test tube, after which concentrated sulfuric acid was carefully introduced along the tube wall. Formation of a reddish-brown ring at the interface suggested the occurrence of terpenoids.

Detection of Tannins (Ferric Chloride Test)

Approximately 0.50 g extract was heated in 20 mL of distilled water and filtered. Two milliliters (2 mL) of ferric chloride solution was added and the appearance of a greenish-brown or dark blue coloration showed existence of tannin compounds.

Detection of Alkaloids

The extract was mixed with five milliliters of 1% aqueous hydrochloric acid and warmed gently then filtered. After filtration, picric acid solution was added to the filtrate. The appearance of

reddish-brown precipitates signified the presence of alkaloid compounds.

Phenolic Compounds (Ferric Chloride) Test

One milliliter (1 mL) of extract was diluted using distilled water and treated with freshly prepared ferric chloride solution. A noticeable change to violet or blue confirmed the occurrence of phenolic substances.

Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis

Determination of Total Alkaloid Content

A sample weighing 0.50 g was dissolved in a mixture of ethanol (96%) and sulfuric acid (20%) in equal proportions. One milliliter of the solution was transferred into five millilitres of tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid. After five minutes, formaldehyde (0.50%) solution was added and the mixture incubated for approximately three hours. Absorbance was recorded at 565 nm. Quantification was achieved using vincristine as the reference standard, applying its known extinction coefficient.

Determination of Total Flavonoid Content

Total flavonoid content was determined by the aluminum chloride colorimetric technique with quercetin as the standard. Diluted extract (0.50 mL) was mixed sequentially with methanol (1.50 mL), 10% aluminum chloride (0.10 mL), sodium acetate (0.10 mL), and distilled water (2.80 mL). The reaction mixture was incubated at room temperature for 30 min before absorbance determination at 415 nm. A blank solution was prepared using distilled water in place of aluminum chloride.

Determination of Total Phenolic Content

Phenolic concentration was carried out using the Folin–Ciocalteu method. Extract samples were reacted with Folin–Ciocalteu reagent and sodium carbonate solution before incubation at 40 °C. Absorbance readings were obtained at 760 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. Results were expressed as gallic acid equivalents.

Determination of Total Saponin Content

The sample (0.50 g) was boiled with 1 N hydrochloric acid (20 mL), filtered, and extracted using petroleum ether (50 mL). After evaporation, the residue was dissolved in an acetone–ethanol mixture (5 mL). Aliquots of

0.40 mL were put in three test-tubes. Ferrous sulfate reagent (2 mL) and concentrated sulfuric acid (2 mL) were added before absorbance measurement at 490 nm after 10 min. Quantification was based on a standard saponin calibration curve.

Determination of Total Tannin Content

Tannin content was determined by extracting the sample (0.20 g) with 50% aqueous methanol (20 mL) under heated conditions for one hour. The filtrate was reacted with Folin–Denis reagent (2.50 mL) and sodium carbonate solution (10 mL). After adequate colour development, absorbance was measured via a UV spectrophotometer at 760 nm using tannic acid standards.

Bacteria Strains

Sample dilution and bacterial isolation were carried out as previously described Taher and Saeed, 2023, *Salmonella* spp, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were isolated from wastewater obtained from the Microbiology Laboratory of Specialist Hospital, Lokoja, Kogi State. A five-step serial dilution was performed on the collected wastewater sample. From each dilution, 0.1 mL was aliquoted on sterile agar plates: Nutrient, mannitol salt, and MacConkey agar. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h–48 h, and to get pure isolates, distinct colonies were repeatedly sub-cultured.

Bacterial identification was ascertained via physical and standard biochemical analyses (Agbo et al, 2019). These include gram-staining, catalase test, oxidase test, indole test, citrate utilization test, and triple sugar iron test.

Gram-Staining

Pure isolates were smeared onto clean slides, allowed to air-dried, and then fixed using heat. Crystal violet was applied to the smears for 1 min and rinsed. After which, it was treated with iodine solution for another minute. They were decolorized using acetone for 30 s, rinsed, counterstained with safranin for another 30 s, blot-dried, and examined beneath a microscope for Gram reaction and cell characteristics.

Catalase Analysis

A portion of bacterial colony was placed on a sterile slide and hydrogen peroxide was added.

Bubble production signified positive catalase reaction.

Indole Analysis

Isolated bacteria were inoculated into tryptone broth which was incubated at a temperature of 37 °C for 24 h. Five drops of Kovac's reagent were added. The formation of a red disc at the broth surface signified a positive result.

Citrate Utilization Analysis

Test isolates were inoculated onto Simmons citrate agar slants and incubated. The development of a blue coloration indicated the ability of the organism to utilize citrate.

Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) Analysis

Isolates were stabbed and streaked into the end and slant of TSI agar in test tubes. The tubes were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C. Results were interpreted based on glucose, lactose/sucrose fermentation, gas production and H₂S formation.

Oxidase Analysis

Oxidase agent (tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine) was smeared with bacteria colony on a filter paper with a drop of reagent. Dark purple colour with 10–30 s indicated a positive result, while no or delayed colour alteration after >60 s implied a negative outcome.

Urease Analysis

Isolates were inoculated into urea agar (Christensen's urea agar) and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. A bright pink colour indicated urease activity.

Antibacterial Activity

Antibacterial activity was done via agar well diffusion approach as described by Osuala et al. (2024). Wells measuring 7 mm were aseptically bored into prepared Mueller–Hinton agar plates with a germ-free cork borer. Both extracts at dosage of 100, 50, 25, and 12.50 mg/mL were dispensed into the respective wells against the bacterial cultures standardized to 0.50 McFarland standard. Chloramphenicol was used as a positive control. Each concentration was tested in duplicate for all bacterial isolates. After incubation at 37 °C for 24 h, after which the inhibition zones were measured in millimeters.

Evaluation of the Inhibitory and Bactericidal Activity of the Extracts (MIC and MBC)

As described in Osuala et al. (2024), the ethanolic extracts' lowest inhibitory concentration (MIC) was evaluated via broth dilution procedure. The extract stock solutions were serially diluted into test-tubes with nutrient broth to obtain doses from 100 mg/mL to 12.50 mg/mL. Each tube received bacterial inoculum and was incubated at a temperature of 37 °C for 24 h. MIC was stated as the lowest concentration without visible growth. MBC was determined by sub-culturing MIC tubes onto agar plates and the least concentration showing no growth on the plate was identified as the MBC.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data from phytochemical analyses were expressed as mean values with corresponding standard deviations. The difference in phytochemical concentrations for the two plants were carried out using an independent t-test. The influence of plant type and extract dosage on antibacterial activity were analyzed using two-way ANOVA. Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$, and all analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics version 23.

Results

Phytochemical Composition

The qualitative phytochemical screening revealed clear differences between the two plant extracts as seen in table 1 and this was further highlighted by their quantitative

differences (Table 2). Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and terpenoids were detected in both *Moringa oleifera* seed and *Azadirachta indica* leaf extracts. In contrast, tannins and phenols were present only in neem, while glycosides were detected solely in *Moringa*,

Table 1: Qualitative Phytochemical Composition of Moringa Seed and Neem Leaf Ethanol Extracts

Compound	<i>Moringa</i>	Neem
Alkaloid	+	+
Flavonoid	+	+
Saponin	+	+
Glycosides	+	-
Tannin	-	+
Phenol	-	+
Terpenoids	+	+

+ present - absent

Higher concentrations of alkaloids, flavonoids, and saponins were recorded in neem than in moringa with flavonoid having the highest concentration (193.15 ± 0.85 mg/g). Tannins

(84.97 ± 1.29 mg/g) and phenols (125.59 ± 0.44 mg/g) were quantified only in Neem extract, as they were not detected in *Moringa*. (Table 2)

Table 2: Quantitative Phytochemical Composition of Moringa Seed and Neem Leaf Ethanol Extracts (mg/g \pm SD).

Compound	<i>Moringa</i>	Neem	t(df)	p-value	Significance
Alkaloid	4.76 ± 0.03	21.31 ± 1.20	-32.45	<0.001	***
Flavonoid	37.45 ± 0.68	193.15 ± 0.85	-156.40	<0.001	***
Saponin	31.12 ± 0.87	47.31 ± 0.99	-104.50	<0.001	***
Tannin	*	84.97 ± 1.29	—	—	—
Phenol	*	125.59 ± 0.44	—	—	—

* Not determined. *** Highly significant at $p < 0.001$

Antimicrobial Susceptibility

The antibacterial test results presented in table 3 showed measurable antibacterial activities against all four test organisms. At the maximum concentration evaluated (100 mg/mL), Neem extract produced largest zones of inhibition, with a maximum of 15 mm against *E. coli*, comparable

to the effect of chloramphenicol. Whereas, *Moringa* seed extract produced smaller zones of inhibition, with the largest zone against *Salmonella* at 9 mm at the same concentration. At lower concentrations, the antibacterial activity of both extracts decreased, although inhibition was still observed even at 12.50 mg/mL, particularly against *E. coli* and *Salmonella* spp.

Table 3: Zone of Inhibition (mm) of Plant Extracts on Bacteria

Concentration (mg/mL)	<i>E.coli</i> (MO)	<i>E.coli</i> (Neem)	<i>S.aureus</i> (MO)	<i>S.aureus</i> (Neem)	<i>Klebsiella</i> (MO)	<i>Klebsiella</i> (Neem)	<i>Salmonella</i> (MO)	<i>Salmonella</i> (Neem)
100	8 ± 0.15	15 ± 0.15	7 ± 0.10	8 ± 0.20	8 ± 0.15	10 ± 0.15	9 ± 0.20	10 ± 0.20
50	6 ± 0.15	12 ± 0.20	5 ± 0.10	5 ± 0.20	7 ± 0.15	7 ± 0.15	7 ± 0.20	7 ± 0.10
25	6 ± 0.20	10 ± 0.25	5 ± 0.15	4 ± 0.20	4 ± 0.10	5 ± 0.20	7 ± 0.15	6 ± 0.20
12.5	4 ± 0.20	8 ± 0.15	4 ± 0.15	2 ± 0.20	4 ± 0.20	3 ± 0.20	5 ± 0.15	4 ± 0.20
Chloramphenicol	15	15	13	15	16	15	15	15

MO = *Moringa* seed extract Neem = Neem leaf extract

Two-way ANOVA confirmed that concentration of the extract had a significant effect on antibacterial activity ($p < 0.001$), whereas extract type (Neem versus *Moringa*) did not show a statistically significant overall effect

($p = 0.093$). There was also no noteworthy interaction between extract type and concentration ($p = 0.623$) (Table 4).

Table 4: Influence of extract type (*Moringa* seed/Neem leaf) and concentration on antimicrobial activity

Source of Variation	F-value	p-value
Extract (MO vs Neem)	3.00	0.093
Concentration	37.20	< 0.001
Extract × Concentration	0.67	0.618

MO = *Moringa* seed extract Neem = Neem leaf extract

Inhibitory and Bactericidal Activity of the Extracts (MIC and MBC)

The MIC and MBC values are presented in Table 5. Both extracts inhibited *E. coli* at 25 mg/mL. *Moringa* seed extract showed a lower MIC against *S. aureus* (25 mg/mL) compared to Neem (50

mg/mL), whereas Neem demonstrated greater activity against *K. pneumoniae* and *Salmonella* spp., each with MIC values of 25 mg/mL. The MBC values were similar for both extracts, with *Moringa* showing bactericidal activity at higher concentrations for both *K. pneumoniae* and *Salmonella*.

Table 5: MIC and MBC of Plant Extracts (mg/mL)

Pathogen	MIC (MO)	MIC (Neem)	MBC (MO)	MBC (Neem)
<i>E. coli</i>	25	25	100	100
<i>S. aureus</i>	25	50	100	100
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	50	25	>100	>100
<i>Salmonella</i>	50	25	>100	100

MO = *Moringa* seed extract Neem = Neem leaf extract

Discussion

This study showed the occurrence of phytochemical compounds in both *Moringa oleifera* seeds and *Azadirachta indica* leaves; *A. indica* leaves exhibited a richer phytochemical profile than *Moringa* seeds. Tannins and phenols were detected exclusively in Neem, whereas glycosides were absent in Neem but present in *Moringa*. These findings are in line with previous reports by Fahal et al. (2018), Omokpariola et al. (2021), Santhi and Sengottuvel (2018), and Elaigwu et al. (2019). However, they contrast with the findings of Seriana et al., (2021) conducted in Indonesia on Neem leaf extract, in which terpenoids and alkaloids were reported to be absent. These observations support the view that phytochemical composition varies according to plant type, species, and geographical location (Gahukar, 2014).

Quantitative analysis indicated significant differences in the levels of alkaloids, flavonoids, and saponins in Neem leaves than in *Moringa* seeds ($p < 0.001$). The higher phytochemical content of Neem may be attributed to its role as a defensive organ. Leaves are continuously exposed to environmental stressors, herbivores, and microbial pathogens and tend to accumulate larger quantities of secondary metabolites for protection (Devi et al., 2017, Salam et al., 2023). Neem is particularly known for producing a wide range of bioactive compounds, including

flavonoids, terpenoids, and limonoids, which contribute to its broad-spectrum biological activities (Sarah et al., 2019).

The antimicrobial susceptibility test results showed a clear concentration-dependent inhibitory effect for both extract. This pattern is consistent with findings reported in similar plant-based antimicrobial studies (Osuala et al., 2024; Kheir et al., 2014). Mohammed and Omer (2015) and is expected because increasing extract concentration increases the availability of bioactive compounds capable of interacting with microbial targets. Therefore, higher concentrations are more likely to produce larger inhibition zones and stronger growth suppression

The stronger antibacterial activity exhibited by Neem may be linked to its higher concentrations of flavonoids and other phenolic compounds. Flavonoids exert antimicrobial effects through several mechanisms, including disruption of bacterial cell membranes, inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis, interference with energy metabolism, and chelation of essential metal ions required for microbial growth. Phenolic compounds can also increase membrane permeability, resulting in leakage of intracellular components and eventual cell death (Mahmoud et al., 2024; Khameneh et al., 2021).

In this study, Gram-negative organisms (*E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *Salmonella*) were more susceptible to both extracts than the Gram-positive *S. aureus*. Although Gram-negative bacteria are often considered more resistant because of their outer membrane, susceptibility may vary depending on the phytochemicals present and the bacterial strain tested. The observed susceptibility of *E. coli*, *Klebsiella*, and *Salmonella* may indicate that the active compounds in both extracts were capable of penetrating the outer membrane and disrupting essential cellular processes. In contrast, the lower susceptibility of *S. aureus* may be associated with strain-specific resistance mechanisms, reduced permeability to certain phytochemicals, or the ability to produce protective enzymes that reduce antimicrobial effectiveness.

Neem exhibited stronger activity against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella*, compared to Moringa. This may be due to the synergistic interaction of multiple phytochemicals present at higher concentrations in Neem. Synergism among flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and phenolic compounds has been reported to enhance antimicrobial efficacy by simultaneously targeting different cellular structures and metabolic pathways (Al-Arnoot et al., 2025, Choudhury et al., 2026). However, at lower concentrations, Moringa demonstrated greater inhibitory effects.

The relatively high MBC values obtained for both extracts suggest that although bacterial growth could be inhibited at lower concentrations, complete bacterial killing required substantially higher doses. This observation indicates that the extracts exert predominantly bacteriostatic effects at lower concentrations and only become bactericidal when sufficient concentrations of active compounds accumulate to cause irreversible cellular damage.

Conclusion

These results demonstrate that *M. oleifera* and *A. indica* are promising sources of natural antimicrobial compounds. Beyond their immediate therapeutic potential, these findings provide a scientific basis for diverse biotechnological applications, ranging from the formulation of eco-friendly food preservation, to

sustainable biopesticide production, and water treatment technologies. However, further studies involving larger sample sizes and higher extract concentrations are needed to validate these findings, explain their mechanisms of action, and support their development as alternative antimicrobial agents and other biotechnological products.

References

- Abubakar, A. R. & Haque, M. (2020). Preparation of medicinal plants: Basic extraction and fractionation procedures for experimental purposes. *J. Pharm. Bioallied Sci*, 122(1), 1-10.
- Adekanmi, A. A., Adekanmi, S. A., & Adekanmi, O. S. (2020). Qualitative and quantitative phytochemical constituents of moringa leaf. *Int. J. Eng. and Inf. Syst.*, 4(5), 10-17.
- Allemailem, K. S. (2021). Antimicrobial Potential of Naturally Occurring Bioactive Secondary Metabolites. *J. Pharm. Bioallied Sci*. 13(2): pp 155-162. DOI: 10.4103/jpbs.JPBS_753_20
- Al-Arnoot, S., Abdullah, Q. Y., Al-Maqtari, M. A., Ibrahim, H. M., Al-Shamahy, H. A., Salah, E. M., Al-Thobhani A., Al-Bana M. N., & Al-Akhali, B. (2025). Multitarget antimicrobial mechanisms of plant extracts: A review of harnessing phytochemicals against drug-resistant pathogens. *Sana'a Univ. J. Med. Health Sci*, 19(4), 292-309.
- Agbo, B. E., Ogar, A. V., Akpan, U. L., & Mbotto, C. I. (2019). Physico-chemical and bacteriological quality of drinking water sources in Calabar Municipality, Nigeria. *J. Adv. Microbiol.*, 14(4), 1-22.
- Banna, Q. R., Parveen, F., & Iqbal, M. J. (2014). Growth inhibitory effect of ethanolic neem leaves extract on *Klebsiella*, *Salmonella* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Bangladesh J. Pharmacol.*, 9(3), 347-350.
- Bichi M. H., Agunwamba J. C., Muyibi S. A., and Abdulkarim M. I. (2012). Effect of Extraction Method on the Antimicrobial Activity of *Moringa Oleifera* Seeds Extract. *J. Am. Sci.*, 8(9): 450-458.

- Choudhury, S. S., Mahanta, A., & Hazari, A. (2026). Synergistic Interactions of Phenolic Compounds with Other Natural Compounds. In *Phenolic Compounds from Medicinal Plants* (pp. 292-313). CRC Press.
- Devi, E. L., Kumar, S., Singh, T. B., Sharma, S. K., Beemrote, A., Devi, C. P., Chongtham, S. K., Singh, C. H., Yumlembam, R. A., Haribhushan, A. & Wani, S. H. (2017). Adaptation strategies and defence mechanisms of plants during environmental stress. *Med. plants and Env. Challenges*, 359-413.
- Elaigwu, E. D., Ogo, O. A., Efiog, E. E., & Oche, O. G. (2019). Effects of ethanolic leaf extracts of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) on oxidative stability of palm oil. *Res. J. Phytochem.*, 13(1), 10. DOI:10.3923/rjphyto.2019.1.10
- Fahal, E. M., Rani, B. M. A., Aklakur, M. D., Chanu, T. I., & Saharan, N. (2018). Qualitative and quantitative phytochemical analysis of *Moringa oleifera* (Lam) Pods. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. Appl. Sci.*, 7(5), 657-665.
- Gahukar, R. T. (2014). Factors affecting content and bioefficacy of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.) phytochemicals used in agricultural pest control: A review. *Crop Prot.*, 62, 99(2014), DOI:10.1016/j.cropro.2014.04.014
- Kashyap, P., Kumar, S., Riar, C. S., Jindal, N., Baniwal, P., Guiné, R. P. F., Correia, P. M. R., Mehra, R., and Kumar, H. (2022). Recent Advances in Drumstick (*Moringa oleifera*) Leaves Bioactive Compounds: Composition, Health Benefits, Bioaccessibility, and Dietary Applications. *Antioxidants*, 11(2):402. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11020402>
- Khameneh, B., Eskin, N. A. M., Iranshahy, M., and Fazly Bazzaz, B. S. (2021). Phytochemicals: A Promising Weapon in the Arsenal against Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria. *Antibiotics*. 10(9):1044.
- Kheir S. M, Kafi S. K., and Elbir H. (2014). Antimicrobial Activity and Phytochemical Characteristic of *Moringa Oleifera* Seeds, Leaves, and Flowers. *World J. Pharm. Res.*, 4(1): 258-271.
- Mahmoud, G. A. E., Rashed, N. M., El-Ganainy, S. M., and Salem, S. H. (2024). Unveiling the Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) Effects on Biofilm Formation of Food-Borne Bacteria and the Potential Mechanism Using a Molecular Docking Approach. *Plants*. 13(18):2669. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants13182669>
- Mohammed, H. A., & Omer, A. F. A. (2015). Antibacterial activity of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) leaf extract against bacterial pathogens in Sudan. *Am. J. Res. Commun.*, 3(5), 246-251.
- Mohanasundaram, P., and Antoneyraj, M. S. (2025). A systematic review of neem flower (*Azadirachta indica*): a promising source of bioactive compounds with pharmacological and immunomodulating properties. *Trad. Med. Res.* 10(7): 41. <https://doi.org/10.53388/TMR20241025001>
- Murray, C. J., Ikuta, K. S., Sharara, F., Swetschinski, L., Aguilar, G. R., Gray, A., ... & Tasak, N. (2022). Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *The lancet*, 399(10325), 629-655.
- Napagoda, M., and Wijesundara, D. (2022). Medicinal plants as sources of novel therapeutics: The history, present, and future. *Chem. Nat. Prod. Phytochem. Pharm. Med. Plants*, 3: 4-18.
- Omokpariola, D. O., Precious-Egere, S. C., Omokpariola, P. L., & Okechukwu, V. U. (2021). Phytochemical and Anti-Microbial Analysis of Metabolites in seeds of *Moringa oleifera* grown in Nigeria. *Prog. Chem. Biochem. Res.*, 4(3), 268-277.
- Osuala, O. J., Igwe, S. E., Ezemba, C. C., Chukuma, C. C., and Oli, A. N. (2024). Prospects of Isolating New Antimicrobial Compounds from Plants: The case of *Azadirachta indica* bark extract. *Ethnomed. Phytomed.* 3(1): 1-8.
- Salam, U., Ullah, S., Tang, Z. H., Elateeq, A. A., Khan, Y., Khan, J., Khan A., & Ali, S. (2023). Plant metabolomics: an overview of the role of primary and secondary metabolites against different environmental stress factors. *Life*, 13(3), 706.
- Santhi, K., & Sengottuvel, R. (2016). Qualitative and quantitative phytochemical analysis of *Moringa concanensis* Nimmo. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. Appl. Sci.*, 5(1), 633-640.

Sarah, R., Tabassum, B., Idrees, N., & Hussain, M. K. (2019). Bio-active compounds isolated from neem tree and their applications. In *Natural Bio-active Compounds: Volume 1: Production and Applications* (pp. 509-528). Singapore: Springer Singapore.

Seriana, I., Akmal, M., Darusman, D., Wahyuni, S., Khairan, K., & Sugito, S. (2021). Phytochemicals characterizations OF neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) leaves ethanolic extract: an important medicinal plant as male contraceptive candidate. *Rasayan J. Chem.*, *14*(1), 343-350.

Taher, A. M., & Saeed, I. O. (2023). Isolation and identification normal flora bacteria from different areas of Ninava governorate. *Nativa*, *11*(2).

Tufail, T., Bader, H., Ain, U., Ijaz, A., Nasir, M. A., Ikram, A., Noreen, S., Arshad, M. T., and Abdullahi, M. A. (2025). Neem (*Azadirachta indica*): A Miracle Herb; Panacea for All Ailments. *Food Sci. Nutr.* *13*(9): e70820. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.70820>.

World Health Organization (2023, November 21). Antimicrobial resistance. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/antimicrobial-resistance>